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HOW EXPERT DESIGNERS EXPRESS SHAPE AND SHAPE OPERATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Computer support for shape design could be more intuitive if the human-computer interface were adapted to the way designers ideate shape. We observed expert designers who communicated shape modifications. The shape terms which the subjects used during their communication were recorded and categorized. The results were compared to the results of a similar test in which the subjects were bachelor design students.

Keywords: Shape communication, Human-computer interaction, shape design.

INTRODUCTION

There is still a need to improve computer support for the design of shape. In particular the human-computer interface should be adapted to the way designers ideate shape. For this reason, it is important to have good insight in the shape ideation processes of designers. One aspect of the shape ideation process is the expression of shapes and shape operations. People are able to express the essence of a shape verbally (Lenau, 2005). The role of verbalization during design is often underestimated (Jonson, 2005). Podehl (2002) collected terms that are used for styling. Our focus is on the broad range of terms that designers normally use during the idea phase of shape design. A study has already been done with design students as subjects (Wiegiers, 2011). However, we assume there are differences in the way students and expert designers express shape. Therefore, in this study the subjects are expert designers. A laboratory test was performed in which expert designers had to describe

shape modifications. The expressed terms were recorded and categorized. The frequencies in each category are determined and compared to those of tests with design students.

Expert designers, because they are more skilled in shape design, possess a richer shape vocabulary. Furthermore, they will be better in judging which the most distinguishing shape details are. Finally, designers who often communicate to each other will understand each other better and quicker. They will need less repetitions and reformulations of earlier shape explanations. They may use a kind of jargon to indicate shape features efficiently and with fewer ambiguity than novices. Therefore, we hypothesize that expert designers need fewer terms to describe shapes properly. However, the character of this study is explorative. Our main goal is to get insight in the way expert designers express shape and shape operations and how their shape verbalizations differ from those of novices.

In the next section, we will explain the method of the research. Then we will present the data that the tests provided. We will analyze this data and compare the results to those of the tests with students. Then we will discuss the differences, and finally summarize the conclusions of the study.

METHOD

We want to know what terms designers use to express shapes and shape operations. Therefore, we arranged a situation in which one subject had to explain a shape to another subject. However, in the idea phase of design, the designers don't think of already well defined shapes. Instead, their image of the shape idea will evolve and change from moment to moment. Thus our interest is not only in terms

Figure 1. Shape terms used by Experts (foreground), and Students (background). The number of terms in each category are depicted as a percentage of the terms of all categories.

that describe the current appearance of a shape, but also in the development of the shape, the way the shape is changed step by step, until it reaches its final state. To reflect this, we chose not to let the subjects describe a finished shape. However, the subject should explain how an initial shape can be modified into a target shape. The setting of the experiment is as follows. Two subjects, *A* and *B*, participate in a test. Both subjects receive a picture of an initial shape. Subject *A* receives also a picture of the target shape. *A* explains to *B* how the initial shape can be modified into the target shape. Based on the picture of the initial shape, and the verbalizations of *A*, *B* sketches an image of the target shape. When the sketch presents the target shape sufficiently, the subjects start with the next object. The test is performed with two expert designers as subjects. One subject describes six shapes. Then the subjects change roles, and the other subject expresses the development of six other shapes. The test was performed three times, with three different subject pairs. So in total we gathered 36 shape descriptions. The used terms were transcribed and coded. After the tests, the terms are categorized and their frequencies are determined and analyzed. Finally, the results are compared and analyzed, to see what differences we can find between experts and students.

We distinguish eleven categories of shape terms (Table 1) according to (Wiegiers, 2008?). Some of these categories are further divided into subcategories. In total, 19 categories and subcategories are used. Below we will give some explanation about the categories.

Category	Description
Shape instantiation	Invokes an image of a complete shape (cylinder, car, pear)
Shape characteristic	Expresses an individual shape aspect (spherical, hole)
Shape operation	Expresses a shape modification (bend, cut)
Location	Denotes a particular location (top, front)
Dimension	Specifies a dimension (length, height)
Value	Indicates an amount (two, half, a bit)
Comparison	Refers to other shapes or values (just as, more than)
Course	Describes how a curve runs (to the left, further, stop)
Confirmation	Tells that a result is correct (yes, ok)
Negation	Tells a change is required (no, however)
Identification	Identifies an object or part (this, it)

Table 1. Shape term categories

Some terms, when heard by a human, instantly invoke a mental image of a complete shape; for

example, the terms cylinder, car and pear. We call these Shape instantiations. The cylinder is a Geometrical shape instantiation. A Geometrical shape instantiation is well defined and abstract. For a car, it is different. Its shape can vary very much, and it is a concrete thing. We call this a Thing shape instantiation. A third case is if pear is used to denote a light bulb. In this case, pear does not denote a real pear, but it tells that the target object has a similar shape. We call this a Metaphor shape instantiation. A metaphor uses the construct of one object to explain another object (Lakoff and Johnson 1980, Fox 1989). Shape metaphors are described in detail by Wieggers et al. (2010).

RESULTS

TEST RESULTS

The total number of terms that were recorded is 1365. These terms were expressed by 6 experts about 12 shapes. Each expert described 6 of the 12 shapes, so the number of shape descriptions is 36. We counted 65 terms that were not relevant for shape design, so 1310 shape relevant terms remained. This makes 37 terms per shape description on average. The terms were assigned to categories. The bar chart in Figure 1 shows the distribution of terms over the categories. The light bars denote the frequencies of the terms the experts used in the individual categories.

The grey bars in the background show the frequencies of the students of the former test. The bars don't denote the absolute frequencies, but the percentage of all terms that is assigned to each individual category. In this way, we can compare the results of the experts to the results of the students. In this test, 28 students participated as subjects. Each subject expressed the shape of 5 out of 10 shapes. This makes 140 shape descriptions. The total number of terms was 5808, from which 5430 were relevant for shape design. This makes 39 terms per shape description on average.

COMPARISONS

In this section, we will do several types of comparisons. First, we will look at the frequencies of terms in each category and compare the results of expert and student subjects. After that, we will compare the results of individual experts. Next the results per object are described. Finally, we focus on

the individual term categories. We will indicate for which objects the terms from a particular category are mainly used.

From the results above, we see that the average amount of terms for a shape description does not differ much between experts and students (37 vs. 39). However, in the distribution over categories, there are some remarkable differences. The top category for experts is the one of popular shape characteristics, while for the students it is the category of Locations. In the top three of categories are Popular shape characteristics and Locations, for experts as well as for students. Furthermore, it contains Identifications for experts, and Courses for students. For each category, we counted how many of the terms used by experts were in that category, and how many were not. We did the same for students and then applied a chi square test ($p < 0.05$). We found the following significant differences between experts and students. Compared to students, experts use more terms of the categories Popular shape characteristics, Identifications, Geometric shape characteristics, Handicraft operations, Emotional characteristics, and Geometrical operations.

At the other hand, experts make less frequently use of terms from the categories Uphold, Need to change, and Shape instantiation geometric.

In the other categories, there were no significant differences. For experts as well as students, the frequencies of terms were very low in the categories Boolean operations, Emotional shape characteristics, and Geometrical operations.

We also looked which terms experts used more often than students, and the other way around, see Table 2. Students have longer lists in the table. Experts have smaller sets of terms they use frequently. For example, they speak more often about a circle than students; however, they use the terms sphere, line and cylinder less often. Possibly, they developed a set of terms they can use in many situations. Another explanation can be, that they have standard approaches to build up shapes, so they can often use the same terms. In the category of locations, it appears that experts tell less often where a specific shape element is in or on. However, they tell more often to where a shape element is directed. In the category of Boolean shape operations, experts used

slightly more adding operations. Students, on the other hand, used mainly subtracting operations.

Within category:	Experts used more often:	Students used more often:
Popular Shape Characteristics	curl rounding dent edge	round arch shape hole block
Location	to	in, on
Fuzzy Value	-	a bit, very, less, etc.
Boolean operation	adding operations	subtracting operations
Course	action terms	order terms
Shape Instantiation Geometric	sphere line cylinder	circle
Dimension	wide long high narrow large small thin	diameter thick times low
Handicraft	bend press roll up	flatten pull cut pinch

Table 2. Shape term that experts used more often than students and vice versa

Below we will compare the results of individual subjects and objects to the average results. We don't want to repeat "compared to the average result" in every sentence. When we report below, for example, that in one shape description Locations were often used, it means: the frequency of Locations in this shape description was higher than the average frequency of Locations.

S1 and S2 both used many Popular shape characteristics and Handicraft operations, but few terms of the categories Uphold, Need to change, Thing shape instantiation and Just as. S3 used also many Popular shape characteristics. This subject used few Courses, Thing shape instantiations and terms of the category Need to change. S4 used many Dimensions, but few Upholds and Geometrical shape

instantiations. S5 applies many Popular shape instantiations and Handicraft operations, but few Thing shape instantiations, Upholds and Dimensions. S6 used many Identifications, but not many terms of the categories Uphold, Need to change and Fuzzy values.

All experts had low frequencies for Geometric shape operations, Uphold, Boolean shape operations, Absolute values, Emotional shape characteristics, Geometrical shape instantiations and Geometrical operations.

The experts did not show much variation in the categories Locations, Metaphor shape instantiations, Identifications, Absolute values, Boolean shape operations and Relative values.

Figure 2. Objects 1 to 4, initial shape (top) and target shape (bottom).

What deviations occurred for the individual objects? Object 1 is a cylinder that has to be modified into a shoe-like object (Figure 2).

This object was often described by Geometric shape instantiations and by Locations. Not many popular shape characteristics occurred, and also not many Courses and Fuzzy Values.

Object 2 was simply a sphere. It had to be modified into a cherry-like object.

Many Metaphors were used for this object, and also Fuzzy values and Handicraft operations. On the other hand, Popular shape characteristics, Locations, Identifications and Courses did not occur often.

Object 3 was a double-sided hook. The target object has one spiraling end and one straight end. For this object, many Popular shape characteristics were used, and also many Courses and Geometrical shape characteristics. We found few Dimensions, comparisons and Identities.

The original shape of object 4 was a sort of block with a higher part in the center. Several subjects

mentioned it a car, and they mentioned the target object a boat.

Frequent terms occurred in the categories Locations, Handicraft operations and Fuzzy values. Dimensions were not often used.

Figure 3. Objects 5, 6 and 7, initial shape (top) and target shape (bottom).

Many Popular shape characteristics occurred for Object 5.

Object 6 looks like two arms. It was described by many Identities and Comparisons, but not by many Locations.

Object 7 can be thought of as a perfume bottle. Subjects used frequently Courses, Changes, and Locations. Popular shape characterizations occurred for this object a bit fewer than for other objects.

Figure 4. Objects 5, 6 and 7, initial shape (top) and target shape (bottom).

Descriptions of the light bulb (object 8) contained many Dimensions, Fuzzy values, Courses and Comparisons, but few Popular shape characteristics, Locations, Metaphors and Changes.

For the chair (object 9) many Thing shape instantiations and Dimensions were applied. There were few occurrences of Popular shape characteristics, Locations and Identifications.

Thing shape instantiations and identifications were heard often for the spectacles (object 10). Terms of the categories Location, Dimension and Need to change were scarce.

Much use of Metaphors was made for the bottle (object 11), and also of Courses and Absolute values. However, not many Identifications, Fuzzy values and Popular shape instantiations occurred.

Finally, the explanation of the dust bin (object 12) contained a lot of Locations and not many comparisons.

If we compare the clay models (objects 1-7) to the products (objects 8-12), it is clear that more popular shape instantiations were used for the clay models and more Thing shape instantiations for the products. This is what we expected: if we mention the name of a product, often its shape is communicated implicitly, because the product's appearance is known by both subjects. However, the abstract clay models have unique forms, which don't belong to the common knowledge of the subjects. Therefore, they have to use terms that implicitly describe shape.

For which shapes were terms of the individual categories used?

In four categories, terms were used for at least 6 different shapes. These categories are Popular shape characteristics, Geometrical shape characteristics, Thing shape instantiations and Uphold. Identifications were often used for object 1 (shoe), object 6 (arms), object 10 (spectacles and object 12 (dust bin).

Handicrafts were mainly used for object 2 (cherry), object 3 (snail), object 4 (boat) and object 9 (chair). Metaphors were particularly applied for object 2 (cherry) and object 11 (bottle).

Thing shape instantiations were frequently expressed for object 9 (chair) and object 10 (spectacles).

Geometrical shape instantiations occurred often for object 1 (shoe).

Some categories were hardly found by particular objects. These were Geometrical shape instantiations for object 5 (club) and object 10 (spectacles), Course for object 1 (shoe), Fuzzy values for object 11 (bottle), Dimensions for object 5 (club) and terms of the category Need to change for object 8 (light bulb).

DISCUSSION

The results show that the expert subjects needed a bit less terms for shape description than the students: 37 instead of 39. This difference is too small to be significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that experts need less terms for the same shape description, is not supported. However, in the distribution of the terms over the individual categories, we found several significant differences. Experts use more Popular shape characteristics, Identifications, Geometric al shape characteristics, Handicraft operations, Relative values, Dimensions and Metaphors. On the other hand, experts make less use of acknowledgements and terms that indicate that a change is required. Also Geometric shape instantiations occurred less frequently among experts. These results show that expert designers apply approaches that differ from the approach of design students, at least in several aspects. We can think of several reasons that may explain the differences between experts and students. Possibly, experts are less uncertain as students and don't need so much confirmation. Besides, they may use more jargon. Their jargon may consist of terms that are clearly defined within their domain, and are not ambiguous, or at least not perceived as ambiguous. Occasional misunderstandings need not be a problem, because the sketches provide quick feedback.

Experts do not only use fewer acknowledgments, they also don't tell often that something is wrong and should be changed. This can be seen as a sign that they understand each other better. Another explanation is that experts don't get nervous from an occasional error. They may be not interested in stressing the fact that something is wrong, but just tell what action should be taken to improve the sketch.

We hypotized that experts possess a richer shape vocabulary. Several observations support this hypothesis. The frequent use of Popular shape characteristics and the infrequent use of acknowledging and denying terms will provide more shape content in the communication. Acknowledging and denying terms may implicitly relate to shape, however, they don't provide concrete shape information themselves. Further support is found in

the fewer use of Courses. It is time consuming to tell somebody how to move the pencil over the paper. Often, the use of courses is an indication that the subject switches to plan B because he cannot find a more efficient explanation.

CONCLUSIONS

We observed how expert designers express shape and shape modification. We compared the results to those of students. On average, experts use about the same number of terms for a shape description. However, there are significant differences in the categories of shape terms that are used by experts and by students. Also among individual experts there are many differences. Furthermore, from which categories terms are used, depends on the shape of the object. In this research, twelve different shapes were presented. This is a too low number to claim that the results can be generalized. After this study, a test has been performed with another set of shapes. The analysis of the test result has been started shortly.

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